

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE EXPERIENCE OF MAINTAINING COMBAT POTENTIAL, TRAINING PERSONNEL FOR HIGH POSITIONS AND PREPARING FOR BATTLE IN THE ARMIES OF AMIR TEMUR TODAY

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Annotation: This article highlights the experience of the great commander Amir Temur in training personnel for high positions and preparing for battle in his army, their significance in the professional formation of officers today, and the components of the new modern principle of organizing the process of higher military education.

Keywords: combat potential, mature personnel, practical experience, corporal, centurion, step by step, council, combat readiness, agility, discipline, competence, knowledge, skills and qualifications, competence, social competence, cognitive competence, components.

Amir Temur is known to us from history, as well as from the Timurid edicts, as a great commander, statesman, strong strategist, who turned Samarkand into a great cultural and economic center, and also the founder of the Timurid state. Amir Temur took control of all spheres in the formation of the Timurid state, one of the most important of which was to maintain the constant combat potential of his troops. In this way, the commander protected the people from the attacks of potential enemies and kept them in peace. Amir Temur, while maintaining the constant high combat potential of his troops, selected qualified personnel and appointed them to positions based on their knowledge and skills.

Commanders did not appear in the army of a strong strategist who established a system of military education and personnel training in his state "by chance", this process was based on strict discipline, practical experience and personal examples. One of the important aspects is that Timur objectively created the opportunity for every ordinary soldier to be appointed to high positions, from being a commander. If a soldier showed courage, he was appointed to the rank of corporal, then to the rank of centurion, as well as to other responsible positions, in short, he was given the opportunity to rise step by step. Timur always held a "Council" before important campaigns. This was a kind of "master class" for future commanders: at the Council, young emirs listened to the tactics of experienced commanders. They learned to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the enemy, developed the skills of working with intelligence, and learned the tactics of conducting a full-scale battle from qualified commanders.

In their time, the requirements for battle tactics or sarkadas were appropriate for that time, including horse riding, archery, accurate aiming while in the saddle, hand-to-hand combat, swordsmanship, spearmanship, and mace-fighting. The qualities of soldiers, sergeants, and officers serving in our armies today, namely patience, endurance of difficulties, and slowness, fairness, impartial approach to punishment and encouragement, intelligence, high iron discipline, and unconditional and timely execution of orders, were also present in the armies of our great commander Amir Temur. With this, we must say that Amir Temur's system was so perfect that during his time the army was never defeated in major battles. The most important part of preparing for battle was gathering information about the enemy. On the maps,

Temur did not start a battle without carefully studying the terrain, [Keren, L., Amir Temur's reign.- T.: 2018.] water sources and roads, and having information about the terrain of the area can lead to great results in defeating the enemy.

Today's modern wars can be an example of this, because the destruction of objects in major battles is carried out on the basis of accurate data. The use of modern information technologies in this area is giving positive results. In short, Amir Temur followed the principles of "Speed, Discipline and Surprise" (unexpected strike) in preparing his army. This system was so strong that he was able to defeat even enemies who were much more numerous than him, as can be seen from this skill that he was a true military strategist.

We remember these qualities of our commander Amir Temur, and it remains an urgent issue for today's military, future officers to be ready and prepared, taking into account the changing requirements for warfare in the theater of modern wars, as well as the use of modern weapons.

In this regard, continuous research is being carried out to improve the competence of our future officers in terms of their own specialization.

Military education includes a set of functions that create the necessary pedagogical conditions for effective professional activity; competence - embodies the specialist's knowledge, skills, abilities and methods of professional activity.

It is also the specialized knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for adaptation to various teams and effective work. Based on the requirements for the qualification of a military specialty, the components of competence are: social competence – knowledge of the requirements of state legal acts, basic documents in the military sphere; cognitive competence - study, analysis, development, study of modern information and communications; special competencies – the ability to make quick non-standard decisions in emergency situations, act with the correct distribution of time, and conduct a full analysis of the military situation that has arisen.

In the professional activity of an officer, along with professional maturity, important professional qualities also play an important role, an example of which is the requirements for the troops of our commander Amir Temur, which were set out above.

In foreign literature, socio-professional constructs are called basic competencies. Basic competencies are personal qualities, knowledge, skills and qualifications that determine the productivity of a future specialist in various situations of professional activity. Work-related problems cannot be solved with the help of narrow professional training or general professional education.

First of all, this is due to the priority of mechanical concepts that reduce the complexity of the relationship between professional qualifications and military education in primary military relations.

In Western Europe and the USA, the composition of basic professional qualifications is determined based on surveys of managers, entrepreneurs and managers of various professional fields.

Today, the development of competencies in officers includes knowledge, skills, qualifications in general professional disciplines (speech culture, language competence, information technologies, modeling and simulation tools); general professional knowledge and skills necessary for measurement technology, technical and technological diagnostics, reading

and development of technical documentation, large-scale activities; independence and critical thinking skills, transfer of knowledge and skills from one type of professional activity to another; coordination of military actions, resourcefulness, endurance skills; quick response, personal responsibility, motivation to achieve success, improving the quality of the task; social skills are communication skills, orientation to cooperation, justice.

Currently, the scope of providing person-oriented professional education is expanding. The requirements for training specialists at all levels of professional education are increasing. This trend requires the modernization of education. The field of professional education involves the development of new approaches to educational standards and the development of qualified students. This requires that each employee also have basic competencies (qualifications, skills, personal qualities and qualities). Basic qualifications are important personal qualities of a professional, as well as lower personal qualities. However, development indicators (quality and efficiency) are important not only within a specific profession, but also in the implementation of professional activities in the military sphere.

One of the modern requirements for the higher military education system through the organization of training aimed at preparing a person for professional activity, the introduction of new strategies is: ensuring the innovative content of the professional activities of future officers throughout their lives, developing non-standard thinking in combination with spiritual and moral criteria when choosing professional solutions.

The following components are distinguished in the structure of the new modern principle of organizing the process of higher military education: socio-communicative, personal-value, time.

The interconnection of these components ensures the creation of a special militarized professional education sphere, characterized by a multi-stage, systematic organization of the higher military educational process based on the advanced design of its content.

Analysis of the main constructs of updating the content of professional education allows them to be structured in the following main directions: general cultural, social, organizational and special.

Thus, the ability of a specialist to perform a specific practical activity is a competency. At the same time, for the psychological analysis of the process of mastering professional activity, such assessment parameters as mastered knowledge, skills, abilities and performance of activities are distinguished.

The concept of competence combines intellectual and skill components as a result of the modernization of the content of higher military education. It is not the individual characteristics of a military specialist, but the components of a multi-structural, multi-functional socio-psychological phenomenon – professional competence.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that in order to develop the professional competence of future officers, it is necessary to take into account the complex of knowledge, motivational-volitional and operational-technological components, their integrative nature, increase their intensity and personal responsibility in the military field, and it is advisable to use the experience of the great commander Amir Temur to increase the effectiveness of this professional competence.

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